

Students' Attitudes Towards The Use Of Games In Teaching Vocabulary For The Second Language Learners

Lina Ali Jarrah, Raeda Mofid Ammari, Ahmed Saleh Abdul Hamid Al-Talafha, Areej Jamil Khalifeh

Article Info

Article History

Received:
May 17, 2021

Accepted:
December 20, 2021

Keywords :

Attitudes, Language Games, Teaching Vocabulary, The Second Language

Abstract

This research aims at identifying the second language students' attitudes towards using language games in teaching vocabulary. The researchers adopted the descriptive approach in analyzing the data. To achieve the study's objectives, the researchers designed a questionnaire distributed to a sample of randomly chosen students. The study sample size was (50) male and female students in Amman Arab University. The researchers conducted a statistical analysis using the (SPSS) program. The outcomes highlighted that there were positive attitudes among students towards using language games in teaching vocabulary. The results showed no statistically significant differences at the significance level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) in students' attitudes towards using language games in teaching vocabulary for second language teaching according to the different variables (gender, university year). Some recommendations were suggested by the researchers.

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.5794577

Introduction

The interest in teaching the second language has expanded due to the new rapid life requirements. Thus, learning languages such as English is very beneficial to cope with global and technological advancement (Chou, 2014). Eventually, second language learners focus on learning vocabulary to acquire the language as it is one of the necessities to enhance their language, especially their vocabulary competence. Second language learners know the importance of having enough vocabulary to express their needs, thoughts whether in speaking or writing. In addition, they feel demotivated while reading and listening owing to the limited vocabulary reservoir. Besides, learners would develop their ability to use the appropriate word in a suitable place. (Gardner, 2013; Nation, 2013).

Regarding teaching second language vocabulary, the teachers find it a vital element in any language. Having enough vocabulary enables learners to master the language; they can choose the proper vocabulary and use it according to the situation. Memorizing vocabulary is not merely a standard teaching method, but they can employ their vocabulary in daily life's communications, addressing people, and writing various texts (Abu Amsha et al., 2017; Rohani & Pourharib, 2013).

One of the characteristics of any language is its large linguistic lexicon, which is difficult for second language learners to master quickly. Therefore, they should reach a good level of vocabulary terms that allow them to communicate. This responsibility lies on the teacher's shoulder as Nation (2013) clarified that teachers should choose the primary (or high frequency) words for the students to learn. Nevertheless, the criteria for selecting the vocabulary that is presented to learners, especially beginners, is as follows (Taaima, 2009):

A-Frequency: common words are learned first. For example, the word "book" is presented before the word "car." Students tend to prefer using words that express their basic needs to others.

B- Range of Distribution: the most used word in a specific country or a city is preferred, for example, introducing the term "mobile" over the word "motorcycle."

C-Availability: learners prefer the word that is accessible to them, which is straightforward to give a specific meaning at the first stages. The students tend to towards learning the word "eat" before the word "discuss."

D-Familiarity: a familiar word to students is preferred over an abandoned, complex, or rarely used word, such as the word "sun" is selected over "intelligence."

E-Coverage: The word that gives more than one domain is preferred over the one with limited sense that serves only specific fields. The word "home" is chosen over the word "house."

It should be mentioned that methods of clarifying the meaning of vocabulary is a significant style in teaching second language vocabulary as Al-Anati (2009) and Odinkaya et al. (2021) pointed out these methods as follows:

- 1-To show the items while displaying a pen or a book when "pen or book" appears.
- 2-Dramatization: The teacher opens the door when the phrase "opening the door" appears.
- 3-Roleplaying: Towards the teacher playing a patient who feels pain in his stomach and is examined by a doctor.
- 4-Mention of antonyms: Towards the teacher mentioning the word "cold" instead of "hot" if they had a previous experience with it.
- 5-Mention synonyms: towards the teacher mentioning the word (enormous) to clarify the meaning (big) if they had a previous experience with the word.
- 6-Association: The teacher mentions the new words which can trigger other related words in the mind. When the word (family) appears, the following terms can be said: husband, wife, family.
- 7-Mention the origin of the word and its derivatives: towards the teacher mentioning when the word (writer) appears so that the teacher can indicate its origin (write), and what terms are derived from this origin related to the new word (write, written, and writing).
- 8-Multiple reading: If a new word appears in a text while the students are reading, they can be asked to read it silently several times until someone explores its meaning.
- 9-Using Dictionaries: students at intermediate and advanced levels can be assigned to search in dictionaries to clarify the new word's meaning.
- 10-Translating into an intermediate language is the last method that the teacher can resort to explaining the meaning of the word, and the teacher should not hurry in this matter. Furthermore, it is possible to explain some words by translating into the mother tongue that the learners understand, especially when explaining words that are difficult to explain in other ways, such as words without nouns or verbs.

1.1 Language games in activating the adequacy of vocabulary teaching:

Language games help to activate the adequacy of teaching vocabulary for second language students. It is one of the best means that provide feedback to learners and supports teachers in their teaching. The employment of these games has led to positive results in many countries interested in teaching new languages and developing their education systems. They have played a significant role in the education process, creating learners' language and considerable growth.

Language processes in various communicative frameworks such as conversations, dialogues, expression, reading, and writing depend heavily on vocabulary. The student's direct use of the language through playing games provides them with numeral names of items and meanings of those things, thereby using them correctly. Games exploit the mental and kinetic energy of the students' minds, and it is also a representation process based on transforming information to suit the individual's needs (Argit, Demirel&Köksal, 2020).

Al Alim (2020) has defined language games as an intellectual or actual activity in which the group plays together with specific laws to achieve entertainment and interaction for the learners through playing crossword puzzles, word boxes, puzzles, and others. Al-Wazzan (2019) considers that language games are a set of directed and organized activities among students - cooperating or competing - aiming to reach students enjoyably and interestingly learn and linguistic elements based on specific rules.

Tibiand Mihoubi(2019) explicated that vocabulary games put students in a competitive environment, train them on language elements, and provide incentives for the development of various language skills within the framework of specific rules established under the supervision and leadership of the teacher.

Choosing language games should take into account several principles by the language teachers. To achieve the desired linguistic benefits, here are some of these criteria (Al-Wazzan, 2019):

- a) To achieve specific educational goals.
- b) To provide fun, entertainment, and suspense to motivate students to learn and use the new vocabulary.
- c) The game should be easy, uncomplicated, and have clear rules.
- d) To suit the levels of learners and to match their language competence level.
- e) To help the teacher diagnose the degree of students' progress in acquiring specific and desired experiences, identifying areas of weakness, and then providing the appropriate practices to help students overcome them.

Language games break the monotony of the traditional classroom atmosphere, turning the class into a sparkle of various activities, competing with learners, trying to win the game, where the students use the language automatically without being embarrassed to make mistakes. During the games, they listen, read, speak, and write. Hence, it becomes a vital means of education, deepens their experience, activates their memory, and develops mentally and intellectually. Moreover, they help learners develop language, organizational, and thinking skills that increase their cognitive and linguistic output. Furthermore, games train them to solve problems and develop their imagination, creativity, and innovation skills (Ghalebi et al., 2020).

Furthermore, many functional roles are performed by language games, such as creating interaction between the students and the environment, developing their personality, behavior, and skills, and activating mental and intellectual abilities. Learners can show their talents, set the values of cooperation, learn social skills, respect others' rights, respect laws, and bring students' concepts closer. Eventually, language learners are provided with experiences closer to practical reality, which contributes mainly to innovative language education to use it spontaneously and understand many language contexts. Thus, the boredom and the shyness they feel are eliminated. Second language students develop a spirit of competition and cooperation. The competition process in games helps them become accustomed to spontaneity in using the language and address it in its communicative framework (Al-Alim, 2020; Scrivener, 2011; Yahya and Al-Menoufi, 2008).

Students need to feel comfortable and more confident in naturally acquiring unfamiliar vocabulary using games in teaching or learning. Learners genuinely enjoy the competition with their peers and enhance their self-confidence in employing the newly learned vocabulary. Nevertheless, the types of games may vary according to the level and age of the learners (Ghalebi et al., 2021). Incorporating games in teaching any language establishes a great learning foundation for students to recognize that vocabulary is fun to learn and not only a long boring list of words to be memorized (Wright, Betteridge & Buckby, 2006).

1.3 The Advantages of Using Language Games

Teaching methodology has undoubtedly changed a lot through many prominent educators' and teachers' experiences. Peters (2020) explains that games are not only activities to fill up time, but they encourage, amuse, teach, and support fluency while learning new vocabulary. This process would enable learners to learn faster as real learning occurs in a relaxed, pleasant atmosphere with the benefits of using games. Another point to consider is that second language learners become responsible and acquire novel experiences through breaking the routine. Language games can stimulate students to learn new vocabulary in a fun and exciting way that increases their friendly atmosphere to adequately communicate and interact together, feeling equal and building relationships (Al-Huwaidi, 2002).

What is more that games allow learners to employ various language skills (speaking, listening, reading, and writing) in different daily conversations. These games increase their self-confidence and favor their learning processes, such as pleasure, enthusiasm, and amusement. Furthermore, playing games offer a decent chance for shy and reluctant students to participate and learn because while playing games, it would be easy to forget shyness. Teachers may benefit from language games to fill in the extra time in any class instead of just squandering it. Second language students can enhance self-education by integrating multimedia in language games and motivating them to use electronic language games. Examples of these computer games are "word puzzles" (Hailah, 2008, Al-Darmawati, 2010).

1.4 The Disadvantages of Using Language Games

Despite the tangible benefits of language games, they do not fulfill the academic purpose in some situations. The vocabulary level of students' repertoire affects playing the game, especially beginners lacking the vocabulary. Games can be time-consuming if the teacher does not prepare them well. Another vital role for the teachers is urging students to cooperate and behave while playing the games.

1. Review of literature:

As for the previous studies that dealt with language games, the following is a presentation of the earlier studies related to the subject of the current research:

Andreu (2015) conducted a study to analyze the possibility of games to acquire and retain vocabulary with Spanish students. The analysis was employed on fifth-grade students in two different universities: three were randomly selected as experimental groups, and two were the control groups. The experimental group studied new vocabulary through games for a whole week. However, the second control group learned the new words the usual way. After the teacher explained the lesson, the students were tested. The result revealed that students of the experimental groups scored higher than the control groups, although the difference was not statistically significant. Hence, this result could be for the short time of teaching.

Mobile game-based language was the interest of Gamlo's study (2019), where he investigated the effect of such a method. Using this style had a positive impact on female students in Saudi Arabia to learn English. The researcher examined students' perceptions of the educational free MGBLLAs: Game Books: Great Reader, Game to Learn English - EnglishTracker, and Learn English Vocabulary Pop Quiz. For seven weeks, the teachers implemented the mobile method on the sample of thirty Saudi female junior students between 18 and 20 who enrolled in the foundation year at King Abdul-Aziz University (KAU). Two questionnaires were developed to obtain the required data. The first is to identify the students' motives for learning English. The second is a questionnaire to explore students' perceptions regarding language-learning applications based on the three mobile games and discover any effect on teacher motivation. The results of the merge revealed that EFL students were motivated to learn English. However, their cause has dramatically benefited as it is taught as a

compulsory course in the foundation year. They must achieve high grades to start studying their preferred discipline. Significantly, the results of the second questionnaire revealed that students view the three applications as beneficial for education and increasing motivation.

Marius's study (2018) explored the problems that may second language teachers and learners encounter in teaching and learning the English language. The researcher applied the analysis in EFL beginners' classes in Beninese secondary universitys, where the two secondary universitys are located in the Abomey municipality. The researcher selected (50) teachers and (300) students. Two types of questionnaires were developed and addressed to both EFL teachers and students. The collected data were tabulated to show the frequency and figures. The outcomes unveiled those students prefer learning the language using games, but many teachers sometimes employ them only as time-filling activities in their classes. A positive impact on EFL beginners was seen concerning their listening, speaking, reading, and writing abilities when these games are effectively applied. Another finding showed that 75% of Beninese teachers realized that using the game to teach vocabulary reduces the students' anxiety in class. The study recommends that teachers teach strategies and techniques to use games to motivate their EFL learners to achieve their educational goals.

Recently, teachers taught vocabulary in the EFL classroom without concentrating on grammar rules. Consistent with previous studies, Pirrie (2017) investigated different teaching methods and retaining vocabulary through games and translation. The sample of the study consisted of (26) students aged between twelve and thirteen. The researcher divided the students into two groups: first, the experimental group, and the second one is the control group. The first group was taught through games, while the second was to translation. The qualitative data: the test and classroom observation, and interviews were collected to answer the study's research questions. The findings showed that both groups learned and retained the new vocabulary. However, the experimental group had a better performance than the control group.

Moreover, the results of the t-tests revealed no significant difference in the results of the tests with no statistically significant. What is more, students were motivated and encouraged to play the games, regardless of their proficiency level, while translation excites the high achievers. These findings may aid EFL teachers in integrating vocabulary games more frequently in their lessons and help students reduce the negative views towards translation.

A study by Tibiand Mihoubi(2019) shed light on the effectiveness and role of language games in teaching Arabic in the primary stage. The study adopted a content analysis method, as it is the most appropriate method for monitoring this linguistic phenomenon. As for the study tools, it was based on observation, which represents one of the tools used in collecting a set of language games. Teachers selected some language games to develop language skills in the primary stage. The results revealed the effectiveness of language games in acquiring writing and reading and acquiring the sub-skills of writing and reading—finally, the significance of language games in developing written expression skills.

The study of AlNatour& Hijazi (2018) attempted to know the effect of using electronic games in teaching English vocabulary for kindergarten students. Their study sample was (100) private kindergarten pupils studying in Irbid during the first semester of 2016-2017 and was distributed into four sections. They were purposefully selected: two experimental groups and two control groups. The results indicated statistically significant differences in the post-test between the control and experimental groups in favor of the experimental group. Furthermore, no significant differences in student achievement are attributable to gender or the interaction between group and gender.

The effect of educational games on developing Second language skills was the interest of Saleh and Hassan's (2018) study, which revealed the impact of these games on second-grade students in universitys in the Gaza Governorate. The two researchers used the experimental method to achieve the goal of the study. For the second elementary grade for 2015-2016, the statistical treatment was carried out using the statistical program (SPSS). The researchers tested the hypotheses by calculating the t-test, covariance analysis, and eta square (η^2). The study found statistically significant differences between the average scores of students' achievement in the experimental group and the average achievement scores of students in the control group in favor of the students of the experimental group. After using language games for the experimental group, the skill of distinguishing sounds and written alphabet, the skill of analysis, and the skill of forming words have increased. The study recommended using new educational methods and strategies that might influence the students participating in the educational process.

The kindergarten children's creativity was examined in Suman's study (2018), which aimed to identify the method of language games in developing the creative imagination skills of the kindergarten children between (5-6) years in Amman. To achieve the study's goal, the researcher prepared the study tools represented in the list of creative imagination skills for the kindergarten child, the educational guide using the language games strategy, and the creative imagination test for the kindergarten child after ensuring their validity and stability. The sample was chosen intentionally, consisting of (50) boys and girls, divided into two groups, each group consists of 25 boys and girls, who were selected from kindergartens affiliated to the Directorate of Special Education in Amman for the 2015/2016 academic year. The study results showed statistically significant

differences at the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$), which is attributed to the gender variable (fluency, flexibility, and originality). The study recommended using language games as one of the educational techniques in developing imagination and creativity skills in kindergarten.

In the same vein, Al-Rabihat's study (2017) elucidated the effectiveness of language games in developing the speaking skills of fourth-grade female students in the Theban region. To achieve the objectives of the study, the researchers used the semi-experimental approach. The study sample consisted of (60) students. The achievement test tool for speaking skills depended on the teacher's guide based on the game strategy. After analyzing the data statistically, the study results showed the effectiveness of the language games strategy in developing the speaking skills of the fourth-grade students, compared to the traditional method. There are statistically significant differences at the significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$) between the mean scores of the experimental and control groups in favor of language games. The study recommended training language teachers to use the language games strategy in developing speaking skills, based on the positive results in developing speaking skills.

Al-Fatiri's study (2017) explicated the efficiency of using language games "Who am I" to improve students' speaking skills at the Orphanage Institute in Indonesia. The research method was the experimental method, and the research sample consisted of second-grade students. The researcher used tribal and remote tests and observation as the direct tools for the study. The research outcomes showed that using language games such as "Who am I?" has effectively improved students' speaking skills. The evidence for this is that the calculation result is greater than the result of T-table or (2.052.77) and that the student's response in the linguistic skill using the game "Who am I" is excellent.

A different way to examine the effect of language games was the Alshaiji (2015) study which observed the development of educational video games and their role in improving the English vocabulary of Saudi students. Video games use the British Council's official website's testing set to teach vocabulary, while traditional methods teach vocabulary to the control group. The sample consisted of (60) Saudi kindergarten students in Riyadh and was divided into two groups: (30) students in the experimental group and the other (30) in the control group. The collected data were analyzed using ANCOVA (Analysis of Covariance). The results revealed that the children in the experimental group performed significantly better than the control group. The researcher recommended that kindergarten teachers rely on video game activities in their classroom practices to improve the retention of English vocabulary for children. Hence, the study aimed to answer the following question: Is there a statistically significant difference ($\alpha = 0.05$) between the scores of Saudi children in the English vocabulary test because of their use of video game activities in kindergarten or not?

Getie (2020) examined the tenth-grade students' attitudes towards learning a second language using different strategies in Debremarkos Comprehensive Secondary University, Ethiopia. The study sample consisted of (103) students randomly selected out of the whole population (1030) for the study. Data collection was through carefully developing a questionnaire as well as interviews with the Grade 10 English teachers. The data were analyzed quantitatively and qualitatively. The study results revealed the positive attitudes of grade 10 students towards learning a second language in new fun strategies regardless of the social factors. Conversely, the educational factors such as the English language teachers and the classroom environment negatively impacted students' attitudes. The researcher suggested that there should be an improvement in the physical learning environment with the government's help.

Regarding the studies implemented at the universities, Elsherbini & Ali (2017) attempted to examine the effect of corpus-based activities on enriching the grammar and vocabulary for EFL students and assessed their attitudes toward it who are studying at Sadat Academy for Management Sciences in Egypt. The sample consisted of 104 first-year students in business English courses. The sample was divided into 54 students in the experimental group and 50 in the control group. The researchers gathered the data from different sources: a grammar test, a vocabulary test, a questionnaire, and semi-structured interviews. For eleven weeks, the former group was taught through corpus-based activities, while the latter students were taught English only by using the textbook. The outcomes revealed that there was a significant difference between the two groups in favour of the experimental. Moreover, they did better than the control group, as the mean scores of the posttests indicated. The questionnaire showed that the students had a positive attitude.

Similarly, Lin (2019) explored university students' attitudes towards learning English vocabulary through team group work in teaching vocabulary. The sample of the study consisted of the non-English major second-year of Taiwanese students. For twelve weeks, the same students were taught with alternating individual work or group work sessions and performed vocabulary learning tests. The researchers developed an Attitude questionnaire where (44) students submitted them once before and the other time after the classroom intervention. Also, they were interviews with (24) students. Results showed that students increased favorable attitudes toward group work, which is less stressful in learning vocabulary.

The current study was distinguished from previous studies in that it was applied to a sample of Second language students, targeting the acquisition of Second language vocabulary at the university level.

The study problem

Acquisition of second language vocabulary for students requires multiple teaching methods and various targeted educational techniques, especially since the usual method in teaching a second language is the use of the standard method or the introduction of simple teaching aids. Since second language students may not understand and comprehend some simple concepts and facts, it was necessary to find a way to achieve the desired benefit of education. The second language learners' ability is limited as they don't have enough capacity to understand all the aspects of language as they are still building their language competence. There should be a modern method that suits their simple linguistic skills and develops their linguistic vocabulary. According to the educational process, many studies dealt with teaching through games due to their importance, including analysis (Peters, 2020). It emphasized the importance of acquiring skills in the process of learning. The problem of the study is determined in answering the following questions:

The first question: What are the students' attitudes towards using language games to teach Second language vocabulary?

The second question: Are there statistically significant differences at the significance level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) in students' attitudes towards using language games in teaching linguistic vocabulary in the Second language according to the two variables (gender, university year)?

3. Objectives of the study:

The main objective of this study is twofold: First, to recognize students' attitudes towards using language games in teaching vocabulary in second language education. Secondly, it is to identify differences in students' attitudes towards using language games in teaching vocabulary in second language education according to the two variables (gender, university year).

4. The significance of studying:

This study aims at revealing students' attitudes towards the use of language games in teaching vocabulary in second language education, so the importance of this study lies in the following:

1. The importance of language games in acquiring second language vocabulary leads to a high level of learning and more effective teaching of the second language.
2. Contributing to teachers' adoption of language games to acquire second language vocabulary in second language teaching.
3. Researching the effect factors of students who are learning a second language is fundamental. Thus, it can assist specialists in designing training programs for these students in this field and knowing students' attitudes towards using language games in teaching vocabulary, which is reflected in their performance.

1.1 Terminology of study:

Language games: a set of purposeful language activities prepared by researchers according to procedures and rules, which is education and fun for students.

Vocabulary: A word that consists of two or more letters and denotes a meaning, whether it is a noun, verb, or article.

Teaching vocabulary: knowing the pronunciation, written, and grammatical forms of words. In addition, to the verbal associations, frequency of use, and appropriateness of words to the context or even knowing the linguistic level of the word, learning its different meanings (senses), and psychological implications.

4.2. Limitations of the study:

This study is limited as follows:

- **Objective limits:** The study dealt with second language students' attitudes towards using language games in teaching them new vocabulary.
- **Human limits:** The sample is limited to second language students at Amman Arab University.
- **Spatial boundaries:** The study was applied at Amman Arab University.
- **Time limits:** The application of the study during the second semester of the academic year 2020/2021.
- **The generalization** of the current study results is determined by the validity and reliability of the study tools.

5. Study methodology:

This study employed the descriptive analytical approach in presenting and describing the data. The study's data aimed to discover the attitudes of language learners towards the use of language games in teaching new vocabulary. The questionnaire was also piloted using a small group of students with similar qualities to the participants in the main study. The purpose was to guarantee that the questionnaire covered the strategies related to learning English vocabulary and that the students could understand the questionnaire completely. Although the completion of the questionnaire took approximately 30–35 minutes, the researchers informed the participants that there was no limited time in completing it.

Table (1)

Distribution of study sample members according to the two variables (gender, university year).

Variable	Level	Frequency	percentage
Gender	Male	26	52.0
	Female	24	48.0
	Total	50	100.0
University year	First year	13	26.0
	Second Year	18	36.0
	Third Year	10	20.0
	Fourth year	9	18.0
	Total	50	100.0

5.2 Data collection sources:

The researchers relied on two primary sources to collect the data needed for the study:

First: Secondary sources: These sources consisted of a group of books and periodicals related to research. In addition, to the information available on the subject on the approved websites on the Internet.

Second: Primary Sources: To obtain the data necessary for the study, the researchers developed a questionnaire related to the subject of the study, based on the theoretical framework of this study and the previous studies presented.

The questionnaire consisted of two parts; the first part included the personal and functional information related to the study sample members, which were: gender, university year.

The second part consists of (12) items to measure Second language students' attitudes towards using language games in teaching linguistic vocabulary.

The researchers used a five-point Likert scale to analyze the study data. The responses to the questions were according to the following scale: (1) = a minimal degree, (2) = to a small degree, (3) = medium degree, (4) = a high degree, and (5) = to a very high degree. The arithmetic means of the study sample members evaluation on each of the questionnaire's items and in each of its fields were interpreted as the following statistical criterion shown in Table (2) was used:

Table (2): levels of questionnaire items

Level	5	4	3	2	1
Approval level	very high	High	Medium	to a small degree	to a very small degree

Regarding the study limitations, the researchers commented on the arithmetic means of independent variables according to their model. The researchers identified three levels (high, medium, low) based on the following equation.

Length of period = (maximum alternative - minimum alternative) / number of levels

$(5-1)/3 = 4/3 = 1.33$, so the levels are as follows:

- Negative attitudes:if the arithmetic means of the item ranged between (1.00 - less than 2.33).
- Neutral attitudes:if the arithmetic means of the item ranged between (2.33 - less than 3.66).
- Positive attitudes:if the arithmetic means of the item ranged between (3.66-5.00).

5.3 Stability of the Study Tool

The researchers distributed the questionnaire to an exploratory sample of (15) male and female students and applied it twice, with a two-week time difference. Then they extracted (Cronbach's alpha) coefficient for the internal consistency of all items of the study tool in the first application, where the value of the stability coefficient by (Cronbach's alpha) method was (0.82), which is a high value, and acceptable for the application. Most of the studies indicated that the reliability coefficient of acceptance is (0.70). The researchers extracted the Pearson correlation coefficient between the two applications. It was (0.73), a statistically significant value, which confirms the application's stability of the study.

5.4 Statistical methods used in the analysis:

The collected data for this study were analyzed in order to answer the study questions. The researchers used a set of statistical methods included in the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS), which are:

1. Cronbach's alpha coefficient to ascertain the stability of the study tool.
2. Frequencies and percentages to describe the characteristics of the study sample members.
3. Arithmetic means and standard deviations to identify the attitudes of second language students towards using language games in teaching vocabulary.
4. An Independent Samples T-Test to identify the differences in the attitudes of Second language students towards the use of language games in teaching vocabulary according to the gender variable.

5. One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) to identify the differences in the attitudes of Second language students towards the use of language games in teaching vocabulary according to the variable (university year).

2. Results and discussion

The collected data for this study were analyzed to answer the study questions. The researchers used a set of statistical methods included in the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS), which are:

1. Cronbach's alpha coefficient to ascertain the stability of the study tool.
2. Frequencies and percentages to describe the characteristics of the study sample members.
3. Arithmetic means and standard deviations to identify the attitudes of second language students towards using language games in teaching vocabulary.
4. An Independent Samples T-Test to identify the differences in the attitudes of Second language students towards the use of language games in teaching vocabulary according to the gender variable.
5. One-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) to identify the differences in the attitudes of Second language students towards the use of language games in teaching vocabulary according to the variable (university year).

3. Results and discussion

A discussion of the statistical analysis result of the current study reveals the attitudes of second language students towards the use of language games in teaching new vocabulary, according to the questions it addressed, as follows:

First: the results related to the first question:

What are the attitudes of second language students towards using language games in teaching vocabulary?

To answer this question, the researchers extracted the arithmetic means and standard deviations of the study sample members' evaluation of the study questionnaire items to identify the attitudes of Second language students towards the use of language games in teaching new vocabulary were illustrated in Table (3) below:

Table (3)

The arithmetic means and standard deviations of the study sample members' evaluation of the questionnaire items where the items are arranged in descending order according to the arithmetic means.

Rank	Number	Item	Arithmetic means	Standard deviation	Attitude
1	1	I believe that language games increase my accuracy, focus and attention in learning vocabulary.	4.48	0.50	positive
2	4	I can identify and match the individual and its opposite through language games.	4.38	0.64	positive
3	2	I believe that language games increase my response speed to learn vocabulary.	4.37	0.66	positive
4	3	I believe that language games increase my vocabulary.	4.36	0.66	positive
5	8	I can interpret the meanings of vocabulary and sentences through language games.	4.35	0.66	positive
6	9	I can read the vocabulary, taking into account the intensity through language games.	4.34	0.69	positive
7	7	I can read the vocabulary of the passage correctly through language games.	4.32	0.71	positive
8	6	I can pronounce the alphabet correctly through language games.	4.28	0.76	positive
9	5	I can read the vocabulary in reverse through language games.	4.26	0.88	positive
10	11	I can learn the names, sounds and shapes of letters through language games.	4.04	0.81	positive
11	10	I can pronounce letters that are similar in shape and pronunciation and distinguish between their sounds through language games.	3.94	0.77	positive
12	12	I can phonetically analyze the sentence into vocabulary through electronic games.	3.92	0.80	positive
Tool / Attitudes of language learners' speakers towards the use of language games in teaching vocabulary as a whole			4.25	0.58	positive

It could be seen from Table (3) that the arithmetic means of the study sample members' evaluations of the questionnaire items ranged between (3.92-4.48), which indicates that the attitudes of the study sample members were positive towards all items. Table (3) results show that item No. (1) "I believe that language games increase my accuracy, focus, and attention in learning vocabulary" scored an average of (4.48), in second place, item No. (4) "I can identify and match the individual and its opposite through language games." with an average of (4.38). In contrast, in third place, item No. (2) "I believe that language games increase my response speed to learn vocabulary." with an average of (4.37).

Interestingly, item No. (12) came in the last place and its text: "I can phonetically analyze the sentence into vocabulary through electronic games.", with an average of (3.92). However, the arithmetic means as a whole was (4.25) for the first question.

The outcome indicates positive attitudes among second language learners towards using language games in teaching vocabulary. The reason is that teaching through playing has helped students to release a mental image stored in long-term memory. In addition, the ability to teach through playing games improves memory and imagination. This methodology, in return, would lead to the retention of the vocabulary concepts. These activities stimulate new ideas by directing the students' minds to the central idea of the topic. Thus, this process makes the learning process meaningful.

The results parallel Suman's (2018) and Marious' (2018) studies highlighting the positive impact of playing games in learning vocabulary in a relaxed and friendly atmosphere. Hence, students are satisfied with their language enhancement and academic achievements as they have better vocabulary retention while learning the language.

Second: The results related to the second question:

Are there statistically significant differences at the significance level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) in the attitudes of Second language students towards using language games in teaching vocabulary according to the two variables (gender, university year)?

To answer this question, the researchers extracted the arithmetic means and standard deviations of the sample members' responses to the questionnaire according to the two variables (gender, university year). The Independent Samples T-Test was applied to the study tool as a whole according to the variable (gender). The researchers used the one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) as a whole according to the (university year) variable. Hence, the results are presented in Table (4) below:

Table (4)

The results of applying an Independent Samples T-Test to the instrument as a whole according to the variable (gender)

Gender	Arithmetic means	Standard deviation	T	Degrees of freedom	Statistical significance
Male	4.39	0.55	1.35	48	0.18
Female	4.16	0.59			

Table (4) displays that there are no statistically significant differences at the significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$) in the attitudes of second language students towards the use of language games in teaching new vocabulary according to the variable (gender). The value of (T) reached (1.35), which is not a statistically significant value.

Table (5)

The results of applying one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) to the tool as a whole according to the variable (university year)

Academic year	Arithmetic means	Standard deviation	Source	Sum of squares	Degrees of freedom	Mean of squares	F	Statistical significance
First year	4.44	0.42	between groups	1.664	3	0.555	1.723	0.176
Second Year	4.42	0.48	within groups	14.808	46	0.322		
Third Year	4.22	0.58	Total	16.472	49			
Fourth year	4.01	0.70						

Results of Table (5) demonstrate that there are no statistically significant differences at the significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$) in the attitudes of Second language students towards the use of language games in teaching new

vocabulary according to the variable (university year). The value of (F) reached (1.723), which is not a statistically significant value. The study outcomes can be justified for second language students because they desire to improve their linguistic ability through language games. These students are highly motivated to learn a new language that requires increasing vocabulary as fast as possible to communicate freely. Students are encouraged to master and learn new languages to cope with the modern development around the world.

These outcomes were compatible with the studies of Getie (2020) and AlNatour& Hijazi (2018), where they pinpointed that gender is not a vital factor in learning vocabulary through games. Games are interesting for young or old learners regardless of their gender.

3. Recommendations:

Learning a foreign language is a dynamic and challenging task that students encounter. Accordingly, teachers ought to find effective methods to facilitate and enhance the vocabulary competence of students. Depending on the study result, the researchers suggest the following recommendations be taken into consideration in the future:

1. Activating the use of language games in vocabulary teaching because of their positive impact on developing language skills, especially vocabulary advancement.
2. Putting language games on CDs and distributing them to students or creating language games websites that are available to students to contribute to self-education.
3. Further studies should be conducted on other samples of students to check whether there is a significant effect of using online games in teaching vocabulary.
4. Holding training courses to encourage language teachers to use games in different educational situations and to make them aware of the importance of these games because of their impact on students' attitudes towards acquiring new vocabulary.

References:

- Argit, G. Demirel, E. & Köksal, O. (2020) Teaching Vocabulary through Games: A Comparative Study of the 4th and the 7th Grades. *Research on Education and Psychology*. 4(1).p 41-53 e-ISSN: 2602-3733
[Research on Education and Psychology » Home \(dergipark.org.tr\)](http://dergipark.org.tr)
- Mahmoud, M. (2008). *Education Design Theory and Practice*, 4th Edition, Amman: Dar Al Masirah.
- Darmawati, R. (2010). *Development of the computer game "word puzzles" to develop the repertoire of Arabic vocabulary*, published master's thesis - Indonesia: Maulana Malik Ibrahim State Islamic University of Malang.
- Al Alim, M. (2020). *The effect of using the card game in upgrading interaction in the process of teaching vocabulary at the State Islamic High School1 Tangerang Al-Janbiyah*. A research presented to obtain the first university degree in teaching the Arabic language, Jakarta: Sharif Hidayatullah Islamic State University.
- Abu Amsha, K., Al-Alawi, M., Snobar, A., Al-Omari, F., Al-Harbi, K. Abdul-Rakhim, R., Al-Batal, Mahmoud and Al-Hadqi, I. (2017). *The training manual in teaching Arabic language skills and its elements to non-native speakers: theory and application*. Riyadh: King Abdullah bin Abdul-Aziz Center for Arabic Language Service, Vol.1.
- Al-Anati, W. (2009). Arabic Vocabulary: An Applied Linguistic Study in Teaching it to Non-Native Speakers, *International Conference on Teaching Arabic to Non-Native Speakers*, Riyadh, pp. 483-557.
- Al-Fatiri, N. (2017). The use of language games "Who am I" to improve students' ability to speak skill (experimental study at the Orphanage Institute of South Aceh), a thesis for obtaining an undergraduate degree, *Indonesia: Zanyeri State Islamic University Band Aceh*, 2017.
- Al-Hailah, M. (2008). *Teaching Design Theory and Practice*, 4th Edition, Amman: Dar Al-Masirah.
- Al-Huwaidi, Z. (2002). *Educational Games: A Strategy for the Development of Thinking*, United Arab Emirates: University Book House.
- AlNatour, A; Hijazi, D. (2018). The Impact of Using Electronic Games on Teaching English Vocabulary for Kindergarten Students. *US-China Foreign Language*, April 2018, Vol. 16, No. 4, PP193-205.
- Al-Rabihat, G. (2017). The Effectiveness of Language Games in Developing Speaking Skills in the Arabic Language Subject for Fourth-Grade Students, *Journal of Educational and Psychological Sciences*, Vol. 1, Issue 1, pp. 17-31.
- Alshaiji, O. A. (2015). Video games promote Saudi children English vocabulary retention. *Education*, 136(2), 123-132.
- Al-Wazzan, K. (2019). Language Games for Non-Arabic Speakers, Union of Arabic Teachers for Non-Arabic Speakers, website: <https://www.uatfnns.com/>.
- Chou, M. (2014). Assessing English vocabulary and enhancing young English as a Foreign Language (EFL) learners' motivation through games, songs, and stories. *Education*, 42 (3), 284-297.

- Elsherbini, Saneia & Ali, Amira. (2017). The Effects of Corpus-Based Activities on EFL University Students' Grammar and Vocabulary and Their Attitudes toward Corpus. *Journal of Research in Curriculum Instruction and Educational Technology*. 3. 133-161. 10.12816/0036970.
- Gamlo, N. (2019). The Impact of Mobile Game-Based Language Learning Apps on EFL Learners' Motivation. *Canadian Center of Science and Education*, Vol. 12, No. 4, pp49-56.
- Lin, Su-Fei. (2019). Students' Attitudes Towards Learning English Vocabulary Through Collaborative Group Work Versus Individual Work. *Journal of Education and Learning*. 8. 93. 10.5539/jel.v8n4p93.
- Marius, Egonleti P. (2018). Practical strategies to teach vocabulary through games in EFL beginner classes: The study of some secondary schools in Abomey Region. *International Journal of Education and Research*, Vol. 6, p 37 - 54 No. 12. English Department, University of Abomey-Calavi, Bénin
- Odinokaya, M. Krylova, E., Rubtsova, A., Almazova, N. (2021). Using the Discord Application to Facilitate EFL Vocabulary Acquisition. *Education Sciences* 11:9, pages 470.
- Peters, M. (2020): Language-games philosophy: Language-games as rationality and method, *Educational Philosophy and Theory*, DOI: 10.1080/00131857.2020.1821190
- Pirrie, Laura A. (2017). *Teaching and Learning Vocabulary through Games and Translation in the EFL Classroom: A Case Study*. Master's degree in Teacher Training. <http://hdl.handle.net/11201/147071>
- Rohani, M. & Pourgharib, B. (2013). The effect of games on learning vocabulary. *International Research Journal of Applied and Basic Sciences*, 4 (11), 3540-3543.
- Ghalebi, R., Sadighi, F. & Bagheri, M. (2021). A study of vocabulary learning strategies among high and low Iranian English vocabulary learners. *Cogent Education*, Vol. 8, Issue 1. Published Online: 20 Apr 2021
- Ghalebi, R., Sadighi, F. & Bagheri, M. (2020). Vocabulary learning strategies: A comparative study of EFL learners. *Cogent Psychology*, Vol. 7, Issue 1
- Saleh, N. and Hassan, M. (2018). The effect of educational games on developing Arabic language skills. *Gaza: The Islamic University Journal for Educational and Psychological Studies*. Vol. 26, Num. 1, pp. 330-354, 2018.
- Scrivener, J. (2011). *Learning Teaching: The Essential Guide to English Language Teaching*. Oxford: Macmillan
- Suman, A. (2018). The Effect of Language Games Strategy on Developing Creative Imagination Skills for Kindergarten Children (5-6) Years in Amman, *The International Journal for the Development of Excellence*, Volume IX, Issue 16, pp. 49-76.
- Taaima, Rushdi A. (2009). *Teaching Arabic to Non-Speakers in Contemporary Society*. New Trends and Required Applications, Egypt: ISCO.
- Tibi, S. and Mihoubi, S. (2019). *language games and their role in teaching Arabic at the primary stage*. Master's Thesis, Algeria: Mohamed Boudiaf University of M'sila.
- Getie, A. (2020). Factors affecting the attitudes of students towards learning English as a foreign language. *Cogent Psychology*. Vol. 7, issue 1 <https://doi.org/10.1080/2331186X.2020.1738184>
- Gardner, D. (2013). *Exploring vocabulary: Language in action*. Routledge.
- Nation, I. S. P. (2013). *Learning vocabulary in another language (2nd ed.)*. Cambridge University Press.
- Wright, A., Betteridge, D. & Buckby, M. (2006). *Games for Language Learning*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Yahya, Hassan Ayel, and Al-Menoufi, Saeed Jaber, *Introduction to Effective Teaching*, 5th Edition, Riyadh: Dar Al-Saltiyah, 2008

Author Information

Dr. Lina Ali Jarrah

Assistant Professor at the Faculty of Arts and Sciences at Amman Arab University

Dr. Raeda Mofid Ammari

Assistant Professor at the Faculty of Arts and Sciences at Amman Arab University

Ahmed Saleh Abdul Hamid Al-Talafha

Assistant Professor at the Faculty of Arts and Sciences at Amman Arab University

Areej Jamil Khalifeh

Assistant Professor at the Faculty of Arts and Sciences at Amman Arab University
